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Executive Summary

The following report summarizes the findings of the work performed during WP3 with respect to the development of quantitative methods used in scaling up phase of the EURITO project. The aim of this document is to serve as a basis for a successful and systematic implementation of the subsequent pilot scale-up phase by outlining the quantitative methods and map them to the indicators that will result from activities in WP3.

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1. Introduction

As public policy makers are surrounded by different sources of data, often in vast amounts, quantitative methods could be considered as the core of the EURITO project. While there are many different datasets, it is the analysis of this heterogeneous data that will transform data into insights for public policy makers.

Ranging from relatively simple descriptive statistical methods to highly sophisticated machine learning algorithms, quantitative methods can come in many forms. The choice and specific implementation of such methods on a given data source are therefore crucial components for answering specific policy questions.

Thus, in this report we first outline widespread quantitative methods, provide their descriptions and link to them to the proposed indicators introduced during our project. For this we discuss the Pilot audit that was performed after WP2 “Exploratory Phase” to extract all methods and algorithms planned to be used in the scaleup phase related to three major steps of data pipeline outlined in D3.1 “Data Collection Methods”:

- Data Collection
- Data Preprocessing
- Data Analysis (Quantitative methods)

This activity provides the Consortium with an overview of available methods and is primarily intended to maximise the reuse of development efforts to avoid unnecessary repetitions during the implementation of the subsequent phases of the project. As project workload was distributed across the Consortium partners that participate in the development of the WP3, such division also allows the coordinated distributed implementation of the system.

Similarly to D3.1, throughout the present report, we build upon the findings of previous works in the European Commission on the application of data science within the public policy context (Campbell et al., 2017).

Further, while an overview of available data collection methods were covered in D3.1, in this report we touch upon the implementation aspects for algorithms of data retrieval and preprocessing methods that stem from the Pilot exploration activities in WP2 and will serve as a basis for the quantitative methods.

2. Quantitative Methods

When analysing the quantitative methods applied in EURITO, we found useful to provide an overview of analytical methods (here and further in this Report we use terms “analytical” and “quantitative” interchangeably) to guide the subsequent use and development of quantitative methods during the scaleup phase. Thus, in the following, we will briefly describe the most commonly used quantitative methods in practice:

- Descriptive Statistics
- Classification
- Clustering
- Association Rule Learning
- Social Network Analysis

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive analysis of data is an important phase of knowledge discovery. Typically, descriptive statistical analysis is the first quantitative method that is applied to learn about the structure of the dataset. By performing descriptive statistical analysis, underlying assumptions about distribution of data can be confirmed or rejected, which will influence the choice of more advanced quantitative methods.

In the simplest form, given an array of numerical values (e.g. person’s income) analysts can calculate the *mean* value for the array to know what are the “middle” values in dataset. *Median* uses a similar concept, except that it represents an actual value from the exact middle of an array, when sorted in increasing or decreasing order.

While mean and median are referred to as measures of *central tendency*, there are measures that show how changeable is the data, i.e. *variability* measures. One of the most commonly used measures of variability is *standard deviation*, which shows how spread out are the points from mean (Tan et al.,2018).

Classification and Regression

Classification refers to the machine learning approach where the algorithm is given some training dataset containing ground truth information (typically, labeled data), so that it could learn how to subsequently classify (i.e. assign labels) the new, unlabeled dataset. While classification methods result in numerical values, the result of regression machine learning are categorical values. An example of a classification task would be to classify whether an incoming email is a spam, given the training dataset of previous emails marked as spam and the text of the incoming email, while a typical regression task is to predict the commodity price, based on historical data (Sidana, M., 2017).

Naive Bayes Classifier

Naive Bayes Classifier is a classification technique, the main concept behind which is that all features of a classifiable object are independent, i.e. they independently determine the probability of an object's belonging to a certain category. Naive Bayes Classifier is considered relatively straightforward to implement and provides comparable performance to more sophisticated classification algorithms.

One of the most relevant subtypes of Naive Bayes Classifier for the purposes of classification of research outputs and other policy-relevant documents is Multinomial Naive Bayes that is used for classification of documents into subject areas based on the occurrence of specific keywords in the document corpus (Tan et al., 2018).

Support Vector Machines

SVM maps the training data onto a multidimensional space to find the best available separation between the data points. In SVM this separation signifies distinction between different classes and can be in the form of a line (linear classification) or a hyperplane (non-linear classification). The objective of SVM is then to find an optimal hyperplane that ensures the maximum distance between different classes (Tan et al., 2018; Gandhi, R., 2018).

Decision Trees

Algorithms based on Decision Trees family use a tree-like structure to classify objects. In essence, nodes of a tree contain the questions about the features of the classifiable object (e.g. "Is the publication appeared in Journal X?") and edges (branches of a tree) represent the outcome of the classification (e.g. Yes or No answer). Finally, the lowest level nodes (leaves) contain the classification decision or a probability of that objects' belonging to a certain class (e.g. subject area of the publication) (Tan et al., 2018).

Boosted Trees

Boosted Trees methods are further developments of the Decision Tree method, that combines several Decision Trees to improve predicting power of the model. The algorithms starts by creating separate Decision trees independently, each of which are given weight, depending on their accuracy. Then, the combination of trees are calculated as the sum of those weights (Tan et al., 2018).

Random Forest

Random Forest method uses similar principle by combining an ensemble of outputs of multiple decision trees, though, it randomly chooses the observations to build its decision trees. Random Forest methods can accept both categorical and numerical data (Tan et al., 2018).

Neural Networks

Neural Network algorithms use a different approach, mimicking how human brain processes incoming information. The approach employs a network of interconnected processing nodes (neurons) that work in parallel to solve a local classification task.

Compared to the conventional classification methods, in Neural Network classification rules are inferred automatically from the given training dataset. Neural Network approach is particularly well-suited for classification tasks when the data is complex and imprecise (Stergiou and Siganos, 1996).

Nearest Neighbor (k-NN)

In this approach, each new object is classified based on the most frequent classes of the k -nearest neighbours. Typically, these neighbours are determined using some distance metric, e.g. Euclidean distance (Tan et al., 2018).

Clustering

Cluster analysis (clustering) is a process of partitioning data into meaningful groups with some common attributes. Ideally, clustering would lead to objects within the same cluster having similar properties to the other objects in the cluster. Again, this similarity between objects is defined using a certain distance metric, depending on the application. In contrast to supervised classification, clustering methods generate labels only from data, thus they are considered as unsupervised classification methods (Tan et al., 2018).

K-means

K-means clustering algorithm divides data into partitions using K number of initial centroids as an input. Then, each data point is assigned to the nearest K centroid, until K clusters are formed. This process is repeated until the centroid points stop to change after the recalculation.

The drawback of this approach is that a user has to specify K -parameter in advance. Incorrectly chosen initial K -centroids may result in suboptimal clustering. In

addition, K-means algorithm is highly susceptible to outliers, which requires more thorough data cleaning procedures (Tan et al., 2018).

Hierarchical Clustering

Hierarchical Clustering is a widespread clustering technique. where clusters are allowed to contain subclusters within or be a part of a superclusters themselves, i.e. forming a hierarchy of groups.

Hierarchical Clustering methods generally divided into two categories, where *agglomerative clustering* algorithms start with individual points as clusters and build up merging them into larger groups in the bottom up fashion. In contrast, divisive clustering methods start with one large cluster containing all the data points, and then progressively divides clusters until each resulting cluster contains only one element.

Hierarchical clustering algorithms generally have the following limitations. First, they are computationally expensive, since there is no potential for optimization. Second, when the merging decision is made between two clusters is made, it cannot be reversed, which leads to suboptimal global partition (Tan et al., 2018).

DBSCAN

Density-based clustering approach tries to find high-density areas of points that are separated from each other by low-density areas. One of the most well known density-based algorithms is DBSCAN. DBSCAN starts by labelling all points as core (the ones that are inside the dense area), border (the ones between high-density and low-density area) and noise points (all the rest points). Then, all core points are connected and form a new cluster, including associated border points (Ester et al., 1996).

Associated Rule Mining

Associated rule mining (or association analysis) is a technique used to uncover hidden relationships between different features of large datasets. It works by generating association rules between items in data that frequently co-occur together.

The strength of each association rule between any two itemsets is measured using two parameters: *support* and *confidence*. Support level of a rule represents how frequently can this rule be applied to the given dataset, while the confidence level means how often do items in one itemset appear in another itemset. For instance, rules with low support would mean that there is a high chance that this rule was generated by chance. High confidence of a rule indicates reliability of the rule (Tan et al., 2018).

Complex Network Analysis

Complex network analysis refers to quantitative methods that aim to analyze the structure and dynamics of complex networks. In essence, a network is a system of objects (nodes) and their relations (edges). Moreover, the following terms are used to define properties of networks.

Degree. Degree of a node denotes the number of relations that this node has with other nodes. For instance, in the public policy context, a high number of degrees of a node that represents a project means that this project has various connections to other research entities: related publications, involved organisations or researchers that worked on this project.

Network diameter. Network diameter is the length of the longest shortest path of a graph.

Betweenness centrality. Betweenness centrality of a node measures the number of times shortest paths between all the nodes in the network pass through that particular node. In essence, betweenness centrality estimates the node's ability to serve as a "bridge" that connects different network parts.

Eigenvector centrality: Eigenvector centrality of a node estimates how important is that particular node within the whole network. This importance is determined by how central are the nodes that connect to that node. Eigenvector centrality gives less weight to the number of connections to the node, but prioritises the quality of connections – a node might have a small number of connections, but these connections might have high centrality values (Savić et al., 2019).

Finally, complexity of networks could be dependent on the heterogeneity of the constituting nodes and edges (multimodal networks), whether the edges within a network are directional, or whether network structure changes over time (dynamic networks) (Parraguez and Maier, 2016).

Outlier Detection

The aim of outlier detection techniques to identify anomalies in data - data points that are significantly different from the rest majority. Typical example of outlier detection would be anti-fraud algorithms employed in banks, which could block credit card transactions if the spending pattern is too different from the usual client behaviour, e.g. due to theft of the credit card.

In essence, outlier detection is not a separate class of algorithms, but a step in the analysis of results from classification, clustering and statistical analysis methods. For instance, in density-based clustering, outliers are defined as points that are too far from formed clusters of high-density and do not belong to any of the clusters (Tan et al., 2018).

Natural Language Processing

Natural language processing (NLP) is a branch of artificial intelligence that concerns the the ability of machines and algorithms to process human natural language. NLP techniques have gained widespread recognition in applications such as topic modelling, speech recognition, language translation, sentiment analysis, question answering (Thanaki, J., 2017).

3. Pre-Scale-up audit results

In this phase, we analyzed pilots produced in WP2 and preliminarily determined plausible indicators and the datasets required by those indicators. Knowing what common datasets and quantitative methods are going to be used for each scale-up helped us to understand how to organize data infrastructure and development efforts within the Consortium. By explicitly stating the bottlenecks and

detailed data retrieval, processing and analysis procedures, we could determine what indicators it was realistic to develop within the EURITO project scope, so that the results would satisfy the RITO criteria outlined in the beginning of the project.

Table 1. Pre-Scaleup phase data collection methods audit

Datasets	Content	Data access method	Notes
Arxiv	Publications	API	Requires enrichment to understand e.g. affiliations.
MAG RDF	Publications, Authors, Affiliations, Citations, Fields of Study	SPARQL query	
PATSTAT	Patents	API, dump	API requires registration
Crunchbase	Business activity	API	API requires registration
Github	Software	Dump	Detailed insights require large-scale scraping.
GtR	Projects, Publications, Organisations, People	API	UK-funded research only

EUROSTAT	Indicators from the other scaleups	API	
COMTRADE	Indicators from the other scaleups	API	Usage limits for unauthenticated users
Meetup	Events	API	
CORDIS	Research projects (descriptions, funding data, etc.)	API, data dumps	
OpenAIRE	Projects, Publications, Software, Datasets	API	
CrossRef	Publications	API	

We note that automatic scheduling and data update of datasets is outside of the scope of the EURITO project, and thus, not discussed in the present report.

Data collection

API access.

Taking OpenAIRE dataset as an example, general data retrieval process from API in Python looks as follows.

First, HTTP request string is constructed by taking into account the necessary record type (e.g. project, publication, software). For instance, OpenAIRE provides a special endpoint for publications that are funded by European Commission projects, which could be accessed via the following URL:

["http://api.openaire.eu/oai_pmh?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oaf&set=ECPublications"](http://api.openaire.eu/oai_pmh?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oaf&set=ECPublications). Similarly, projects funded by European Commissions can be

accessed through performing an API call as follows:

“http://api.openaire.eu/oai_pmh?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oaf&set=ECProjects”.

Second, the constructed URL string is passed to the API, using Session methods of the Requests Python library (<https://2.python-requests.org/en/master/>). The obtained response is then parsed using BeautifulSoup module (<https://www.crummy.com/software/BeautifulSoup/bs4/doc/index.html>), which allows to quickly find and iterate over XML tags (through *find_all()* method), contained in the response text.

In many cases, iterating over large datasets via API may require support for pagination, since all results can not be returned in one response. This is typically achieved either via adding to request URL a resumption token string obtained from the last response (*&resumptionToken=* parameter) or through programmatically setting the page number and page size (*?page=* and *?size=* parameters).

Data dump access

In case of directly accessing data dumps, Python’s open-source Pandas library (<https://pandas.pydata.org/>) has convenient modules to read and write the majority of common data formats (https://pandas.pydata.org/pandas-docs/stable/user_guide/io.html).

Data preprocessing

Data preprocessing starts after data is retrieved from an API or a file is loaded into Python module. In most cases, data preprocessing consists of merging columns of different tables or filtering data by some attribute. Often, data cleaning methods are employed to remove erroneous or missing data.

For instance, in Pilot 8 “Knowledge Flow”, we first extracted the list of Horizon 2020 projects from the XLS file, created a dictionary of projects where key is equal to the project ID and dictionary value is equal to the the rest of the project related information (project description, participant organisations, received funding). We then extracted publications from OpenAIRE API and created the list of publications that

contained project IDs. We then merged these two datasets and converted links between projects and publications into a graph representation. This is an example of data preprocessing step, which is often a prerequisite before any data analysis could be performed.

Regarding the prototyping of data preprocessing activities, we note that Jupyter Notebook tool (<https://jupyter.org/>) is especially applicable. Practically, Jupyter Notebook allows one to breakdown each of data preprocessing steps and show related output during the each step of data modification. However, for robust implementations of the data processing, we will develop using raw python in order to ensure that data processing steps are atomic and unit-testable, as is standard practice in data development environments.

Data analysis

Having defined in Section 2 the commonly used quantitative methods, Table 2 maps these quantitative methods to preliminary indicators identified during the Pilot Scale-Up selection phase. In addition, we break down which tasks with proposed indicators do these quantitative methods accomplish and the references to Python libraries relevant to each of the quantitative methods.

Table 2. Quantitative methods within proposed indicators

Quantitative Method	Preliminary Indicator	Task within Indicator	Python library used
Descriptive statistics	Activity, funding in mission field, evolution of activity over time and disciplinary breakdown of mission field	After entities are filtered by mission field, provides descriptive statistics on activity, funding, dynamics over time and disciplinary breakdown	Scikit-learn (https://scikit-learn.org/stable/) Pandas (https://pandas.pydata.org)

Complex network analysis	Project, organisation centrality	Find central organisations in EC R&I ecosystem	iGraph (https://igraph.org/python/)
	Distribution of emergent technology activity by relevant enriched category (industry, sdg, discipline)	Create topic co-occurrence network and detect topic communities (disciplines) within the created network	NetworkX (https://networkx.github.io/)
	K-Factor (research output novelty)	Create co-occurrence network of publication keywords to determine how each of them contributes to the overall network	Graph-tool (https://graph-tool.skewed.de/)
Natural language processing	Level of activity in emerging technology and country / region / year etc,	Find entities related to the search query, topic modelling.	spicy (https://spacy.io/), gensim (https://radimrehurek.com/gensim/)
Clustering	Technological transformation	Groups keywords by their co-occurrence	Scikit-learn, Louvain(https://github.com/taynaud/python-louvain)
Regression	Nowcasting of indicators	Predicts future values of indicators based on historical data	Scikit-learn

Data Infrastructure Setup

After the analysis of datasets and quantitative methods used to produce indicators, EURITO data infrastructure is setup as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Data exchange model within the EURITO data infrastructure

We separated raw data from the external original sources from the EURITO's data pipeline. Besides visualisations of the generated indicators, by design, users are enabled an access to the original data sources directly from the EURITO frontend: either through direct link to datasets or through constructed API calls to the original data source API.

The EURITO backend system itself would perform the following functions:

- collect data from original sources for preprocessing
- preprocess data before the analysis
- use quantitative methods outlined above to generate indicators
- prepare indicator data for visualisation output
- send data for storage and retrieve from the EURITO database

Development stack

Batch jobs in EURITO data pipeline are automated using Luigi pipeliness Python package (<https://github.com/spotify/luigi>).

Ensuring the quality of the developed modules in the project is performed using unit-testing methodology. Unit-testing is an approach to test portions of code, by systematically providing input data and examining whether these portions provide the correct and expected output. In the project we use PyTest library in Python (<https://docs.pytest.org/en/latest/>).

Amazon Web Services (AWS) S3 (<https://aws.amazon.com/s3/>) is used as a main system to store EURITO backend logic and databases. AWS provides a scalable, reliable and relatively inexpensive access to data, while providing flexibility in deploying necessary data infrastructure.

The choice of database management system is largely motivated by the quantitative methods of the indicator that this database will be supporting. Majority of datasets are stored in MySQL databases (<https://www.mysql.com/>), while indicators that rely on complex network use Neo4j (<https://neo4j.com/>) for performance considerations. Neo4j uses a different storage paradigm compared to MySQL and supports graph structure natively. In essence, all data in Neo4j is either a node, an edge or a data attribute of a node. This allows to yield faster performance when retrieving connected data (e.g. find related articles), as Neo4j does not have to iterate through indexes when performing CRUD operations on related nodes.

Conversion between MySQL database logic and data processing methods in Python code is supported using Object Relational Mapping functionality within Python's SQLAlchemy library (<https://www.sqlalchemy.org/>).

Search within EURITO datasets is enabled via Elasticsearch search engine (<https://www.elastic.co/products/elasticsearch>). Elasticsearch is one of the most widely adopted search engines today, due to its scalability, fast performance and ability to search different types of documents. Elasticsearch uses REST API paradigm and supports operations with JSON.

Finally, we use Flask web-framework server (<http://flask.pocoo.org/>) as middleware to handle requests and responses to and from the EURITO frontend web-application.

Conclusion

This report describes performed activities within WP3 with regards to developing quantitative methods to support indicator scale-up in the subsequent phases of the EURITO project. First, background descriptions of commonly used quantitative methods were provided. Second, we summarise the data collection, data preprocessing and quantitative methods that were used in the Pilot development phase and will be used in the Scale-up phase. Mapping of quantitative methods to respective indicators, tasks within indicators and their implementations was provided. Finally, based on the overview of quantitative methods, we described a necessary data infrastructure and development stacks with relevant technological alternatives.

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